

A Global Biodata Coalition White Paper

Working Cooperatively for Global Biodata Resource Sustainability

Executive Summary

Biodata resources are essential to the global research endeavour in the life sciences and biomedicine, but the current funding for these resources is fragmented, uncoordinated and far from secure. Sustaining the global biodata infrastructure is a critical and growing challenge that requires urgent and cooperative action.

The Global Biodata Coalition (GBC) developed this White Paper as a step to meet this challenge. It identifies the key areas where research funders need to work with biodata resources and wider stakeholder communities to build solutions. It provides a framework through which GBC and its member funders will work to advance these goals.

The White Paper calls for the adoption of nine foundational principles as the framework for cooperative funding models to enhance sustainability of the global biodata infrastructure as listed on the next page.

Cooperative funding to sustain the global biodata infrastructure: Nine Foundational Principles

1. Those who fund life science research share responsibility for ensuring that data resources are sustained.
2. Life science research funders of all types should contribute to biodata resource sustainability.
3. Funders should contribute through means that are appropriate to their situation.
4. Sustainability will be required both for existing resources and for new resources that are established to respond to new data types and technologies.
5. Funding approaches should not require payment at the point of use of a biodata resource unless this is the only viable option. Where payments are required, they should be equitable and fair, and should not restrict access to data based on ability to pay.
6. Models for sustainability must allow for the participation of funders whose funds cannot move across national borders.
7. Biodata resources should develop governance structures that support the interests of funding organisations and the institutions that host biodata resources.
8. Biodata resources should ensure data and metadata are as open as possible and as closed as necessary—balancing the need to reduce friction and costs to access for users whilst providing proportionate governance and safeguards where required.
9. All biodata resources should have a clear strategy for sustainability, including appropriate succession plans.

Building on these Principles, the White Paper then makes detailed recommendations for:

- Developing, testing and implementing new and innovative cooperative funding mechanisms
- Coordinating support for research funders to sustain the global biodata resource infrastructure

GBC will work with research funders, biodata resource managers and other stakeholders to implement this White Paper.

GBC will use this White Paper to stimulate discussion and debate among these groups and use the outputs on an ongoing basis to shape our approach and drive activities at national, regional and global levels to address this critical challenge.

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Introduction

1.1 Biodata resources: a crucial global infrastructure under threat

1. Researchers across the life sciences and biomedicine depend upon a global infrastructure of biodata resources to store, preserve, curate and provide access to research data. These biodata resources include deposition databases, which store primary research data, and knowledgebases that curate these data and enable their widespread use in research (see Anderson et al. 2017).
2. Biodata resources are accessed and used by hundreds of thousands of researchers all over the world. They play a critical role in advancing scientific discovery and its application for societal benefit, and provide immense value to the user communities they serve and to society more broadly. For example, an independent evaluation published in 2021 to assess the value and impact of data resources provided by the EMBL European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI) estimated that these resources had directly underpinned research impacts valued at £1.3 billion annually that could not otherwise have been realised (see Beagrie and Houghton 2021). The study, which updated an earlier 2015 report, also estimated that the benefit in terms of efficiency gains to users and their funders was worth between £2.6 billion and £11 billion per annum worldwide. Based on an estimated annual expenditure of £110 million, the study indicated these biodata resources provide a substantial return on investment.
3. Biodata resources are also critical in supporting the drive for open science, which seeks to ensure research data and other research outputs can be accessed and re-used by researchers the world over in ways that maximise their benefit. In supporting the research communities that they serve, biodata resources play a critical role in enabling key datasets across the life sciences and biomedicine to be open and FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable), and in driving the uptake of community data standards. As such, they are crucially important to the successful implementation of the increasingly

stringent open data policies that are being set by funders, publishers and research institutions.

4. Despite the fundamental importance of the global biodata infrastructure, current funding arrangements to maintain and develop component biodata resources are fragmented and uncoordinated at a global level. Many biodata resources do not have secure long-term funding, and depend on periodic short-term competitive grant funding, sometimes from a single or limited pool of funders (see Bourne et al. 2015). This constrains their ability to plan for the long-term and to attract and retain skilled staff. Whilst several funders have provided extensive long-term support for particular biodata resources, these resources may still find themselves in a perilous position should budgets fall or the strategic priorities change of funders on whom they depend for ongoing support.
5. The funding contributions for resources do not reflect their global usage. For many globally-relevant biodata resources, a single national funder or small cohort of public and charitable funders is providing ongoing support for the benefit of users worldwide. Many countries and funders (including public, philanthropic and private sectors funders) whose researchers depend critically on particular biodata resources are currently not contributing to the support and maintenance of this infrastructure.
6. Current funding challenges for biodata resources are compounded by the ever-growing rise in the volume and complexity of research data, and the rapid emergence of data-intensive science including AI and machine learning. In addition, increasingly robust open data policies from funders and publishers place increasing pressure on biodata resources to support researchers in fulfilling these mandates. The growth of the open science movement has seen the development of new community standards, such as the FAIR and TRUST principles (see Wilkinson et al. 2016, Lin et al. 2020); which resources are expected to implement, and the emergence of new accreditation systems for resources, such as Core Trust Seal (see L'Hours et al. 2019). Over and above this, there is a growing expectation on resources to provide data and services in forms that are fully 'AI-ready' which can represent a significant challenge. All of these elements place increased demands and pressure on the infrastructure, many parts of which are already under-resourced and at risk.

7. To be 'sustainable', individual biodata resources and the global biodata infrastructure as whole need to be maintained and developed over the long-term to meet the evolving needs of user communities. This White Paper focuses primarily on ensuring the provision of stable and secure long-term funding to ensure sustainability. It is recognised that sustainability has many aspects that extend beyond funding: for example, it requires effective governance, ongoing maintenance of technical and service standards, and the ability to recognise and respond to rapidly evolving scientific and technical developments. Provision of ongoing funding is, however, absolutely fundamental to ensuring a resource is able to maintain its operations over time and to fulfil all of the elements it needs to provide to be 'sustainable'.
8. The need for resources to develop approaches to enhance sustainability has long been recognised. Several reports from international and national working groups over recent years have explored this issue—including groups convened by the OECD and US National Academies (see OECD 2017 and National Academies 2020). In Europe, the ELIXIR infrastructure has brought together Europe's biodata resources and encouraged a coordinated approach to manage and sustain the European biodata infrastructure—including through identifying ELIXIR core data resources (see Drysdale et al. 2020). But few concrete solutions to the challenges of long-term funding and sustainability have yet emerged.
9. The current lack of stable long-term funding may result in more biodata resources deciding to charge access fees or introduce other access constraints for some types of users or services. Whilst such models may be appropriate for some resources in some circumstances, there is a risk they will particularly disadvantage researchers in less well resourced settings. Maintaining open and unrestricted access to research data is key to ensuring global equity and maximising global benefit, and creates an imperative for the world's funders to work together to address this challenge.

1.2 The Global Biodata Coalition

10. The Global Biodata Coalition (GBC) is a forum for research funders to better coordinate and share approaches for the efficient management and growth of biodata resources worldwide. The GBC aims to stabilise and ensure sustainable financial support for the global biodata infrastructure, and is the first dedicated organisation established by funders for this purpose. It currently has ten member funders as listed below.

GBC Members (as at November 2024)

African Academy of Sciences

Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (UK)

Chan Zuckerberg Initiative

European Molecular Biology Laboratory

Genome Canada

National Institutes of Health (USA)

National Science Foundation (USA)

Research Council of Norway

State Secretariat for Education Research & Innovation SERI (Switzerland)

Wellcome

11. As a key part of its work, the GBC designates and works with a set of Global Core Biodata Resources (GCBRs). GCBRs are biodata resources that are of fundamental importance to the global research enterprise in the life sciences and the long term preservation of biological data. Through selection rounds in 2022 and 2023, the GBC has identified a list of 52 GCBRs. It has established the GCBR Forum to bring together senior leaders from these biodata resources to share experience and best practices in relation to sustainability, and to work with GBC and its members to identify and set in place more sustainable funding approaches.
12. As critical nodes within this infrastructure, strengthening the funding and long-term security of GCBRs will enhance the sustainability of the infrastructure as a whole and the identification of more sustainable funding approaches and strategies will benefit other biodata resources. However, whilst working with a defined set of GCBRs forms a core part of GBC's work, it also aims to characterise the entire global infrastructure of biodata resources, and engage resources of all types in its work. In 2023, the GBC published a global inventory of biodata resources, providing a fuller picture of the global landscape of biodata resources than has been available previously (see Imker et al 2023). Using a machine learning-enabled natural language processing approach to mine the literature, the work identified a corpus of 3,112 unique resources from articles published between 2011 and 2021.
13. GBC endorses the principle that data should be as open as possible and as closed as necessary. The focus of GBC to date has been on biodata resources that provide open and unrestricted access to data, and the initial rounds of GCBR selection have been limited to resources of this type. GBC recognises that many types of life science and biomedical data cannot be shared openly, and that controls and limits on access are essential where data relate to human subjects or present risks to biodiversity or biosecurity. It plans to extend future GCBR selection rounds to include resources that provide managed access to these data types, in line with the FAIR principles and other international standards, including the CARE principles for data sovereignty. (see Carroll et al 2020)

1.3 Developing the GBC White Paper

14. This GBC White Paper resulted from the discussions of an expert working group comprised of representatives from GBC member organisations. The ideas emerging from these discussions were developed further with the input of GBC's key governance and advisory bodies, and through consultation with GBC's wider stakeholder communities. The process is summarised briefly in Appendix A. A more detailed description, including a fuller summary of the outcomes of the community consultation, is available in the linked supplementary document.

1.4 Aims of the White Paper

15. This White Paper sets out a framework for the development of cooperative approaches to ensure the long-term funding and sustainability of the global biodata resource infrastructure. This framework will guide GBC's work with its partners and stakeholders to advance this goal. The intended audience for this paper includes research funders of all types, biodata resource managers, the broader life science research community and policy makers at national and international levels.
16. The GBC will use this White Paper to stimulate discussion and debate on the challenge of biodata resource sustainability, and to secure the participation and support of funders, infrastructure providers, users and policy makers across the globe to secure and strengthen the global infrastructure. It is hoped that the White Paper will also inspire other organisations to take forward efforts at national and global levels that aim to provide enhanced and more sustainable funding for critical biodata resources.

2. Funding and Sustaining the Global Biodata Resource Infrastructure: A Framework for Action

17. Securing the long-term funding and sustainability of the global biodata resource infrastructure is a complex, global challenge that requires cooperative approaches between research funders and biodata resource providers. This White Paper proposes priorities for collective action in three key areas as described in the sections that follow:
- Adopting foundational principles for the design of cooperative funding approaches.
 - Developing, testing and implementing new cooperative funding mechanisms
 - Coordinating support for research funders to sustain the global biodata resource infrastructure.

2.1 Adopting foundational principles for the design of cooperative funding approaches

18. It is important that global efforts to address the sustainability challenge are guided by a common vision and set of agreed parameters that reflect the key features that a sustainable biodata infrastructure requires. We identify a series of premises and principles that together provide a foundation for the design of cooperative funding approaches. The premises are key observations or assumptions in relation to the global biodata infrastructure landscape. The Principles build on these Premises, providing specific positions to guide models for global cooperation amongst funders and biodata resource managers. As such they are relevant to both of these communities.

Five Core Premises

19. The five core premises highlight the crucial importance of the global biodata infrastructure and the importance and complexity of the sustainability challenge. These are summarised below, and elaborated further below.

Biodata Resource Infrastructure: Five Core Premises

1. **Biodata resources are essential to life science research globally, individually and collectively**
2. **Coordinating biodata resource sustainability will bring efficiencies.**
3. **It will be necessary to define which biodata resources are included within global efforts to ensure long term sustainability.**
4. **Sustainability in biodata resources centres upon sustainable funding.**
5. **Solving the sustainability problem will require new and innovative approaches.**

20. First, all life sciences research—whether experimental or observational, wet-lab or computational, involves the management of data. This includes data generated de novo to address a research question and pre-existing data that are used for comparison or reference. Biodata resources are essential tools for enabling data management—including submission of newly generated data, publication of derived or curated data, or use of pre-existing data. They have value to science and society individually and collectively, with the benefits of individual resources amplified across the connected biodata resource infrastructure.
21. Second, broader and more coordinated global support for biodata resources should offer efficiencies which benefit all research funders, as all funders support researchers who access and use biodata

resources. Such coordination will allow improvements to user-facing interfaces and services and additional investment in technical infrastructure, lowering the burden of access and reducing project costs; and may also help identify and remove some unnecessary redundancy.

22. Third, globally coordinated efforts will require agreement of which biodata resources are within scope for support. GBC is working to help funders identify biodata resources that are widely used in life science research and are priorities for sustainability, as well as to characterise the broader global infrastructure. Individual funders will determine their own priorities. In addition to supporting biodata resources which fulfil the criteria to be Global Core Biodata resources, many funders will also decide to prioritise support for more niche data resources that are of strategic importance to their communities.
23. Fourth, the sustained operation of a biodata resource reflects many factors that go beyond funding—such as maintaining an active and engaged user community or developing data linkages with external databases. All of these elements require that there is—at the centre—a viable, stable and sustained biodata resource around which activities can coalesce, and in which the users can have confidence.
24. Finally, the complex challenges around sustainability will require creative approaches. Extensive change is required: funding organisations must adapt their programmes; biodata resource managers will need to work in new ways; and the wider scientific community must place greater value upon biodata resources. These transitions will be difficult, but will add value to life science, and enhance global cooperation for the benefit of all.

Nine Foundational Principles

25. Taking these premises as a basis, we propose nine principles below for the design of cooperative funding approaches.

Biodata Resource Infrastructure: Nine Foundational Principles

1. Those who fund life science research share responsibility for ensuring that data resources are sustained.
2. Life science research funders of all types should contribute to biodata resource sustainability.
3. Funders should contribute through means that are appropriate to their situation.
4. Sustainability will be required both for existing resources and for new resources that are established to respond to new data types and technologies.
5. Funding approaches should not require payment at the point of use of a biodata resource unless this is the only viable option. Where payments are required, they should be equitable and fair, and should not restrict access to data based on ability to pay.
6. Models for sustainability must allow for the participation of funders whose funds cannot move across national borders.
7. Biodata resources should develop governance structures that support the interests of funding organisations and the institutions that host biodata resources.
8. Biodata resources should ensure data and metadata are as open as possible and as closed as necessary—balancing the need to reduce friction and costs to access for users whilst providing proportionate governance and safeguards where required.
9. All biodata resources should have a clear strategy for sustainability, including appropriate succession plans.

26. At the heart of these Principles is the proposition that sustainability of the global biodata infrastructure is the collective responsibility of all life sciences research funders. The first and second principles emphasise that as biodata resources are essential tools for life science research, their sustainability should be of concern to all research funders and the international research community more broadly.
27. As such, it is the responsibility of all research funding organisations to support, in significant, tangible and persistent ways, the sustainability of biodata resources—whether by funding biodata resources directly or by working with other bodies at national and international levels. As this infrastructure is a global good, it should also be of concern to international, cross-governmental organisations. If the costs are shared across all life science research funders, the burden on each funder will be manageable. And if broadly shared, the cost of sustainability relative to other aspects of research funding will remain very low.
28. With regard to the second principle, the definition of ‘research funder’ should be set broadly. Whilst the current membership of GBC is currently drawn from government-linked national and international research funding bodies and from the larger research foundations, organisations that fund life science research also include philanthropies, commercial entities, citizen advocacy groups, universities, and more. They all depend on the sustainability of the biodata resource infrastructure, and cooperative funding approaches should seek to include and account for the needs of the many and varied organisations that fund research.
29. Further to this point, the third principle acknowledges that any cooperative approaches need to provide flexibility and allow for funders to contribute in different ways depending on their remits, means and modes of operation. Whilst some funders will be able to provide direct funding contributions to biodata resources, others will have legal or administrative barriers to their funding remits that may necessitate the use of local or in-kind contributions, such as the hosting of components of a biodata resource or the secondment of staff. Similarly, for low and middle-income countries, mechanisms are needed to facilitate their participation and develop capacity to contribute to the global infrastructure.
30. The fourth principle notes that new biodata resources will emerge over time, both to address existing gaps in biodata resource provision and

to account for the emergence of new research areas and analytical platforms. Although establishing sustainability in a new biodata resource from the outset will likely be easier than adapting the funding and operational arrangements for an existing resource, both types of resources must remain as targets for sustainability interventions despite the challenges.

31. The fifth principle prioritises funding models that enable biodata resources to make their core data and services available to users of all types without payment at the point of use. In general, models which involve the direct allocation of funds from funding organisations to support the operation of biodata resources, will offer the least “friction” for those using the resources and allow for the greatest transparency. In contrast, indirect mechanisms—such as charging researchers at the point of use for data services (such as deposition and retrieval) with subsequent reimbursement through grant agreements—would bring complexity and friction for both funders and researchers and may discourage researchers from making full use of data resources (including for sharing their data) if doing so requires them to allocate funds from research budgets or costs too much time.
32. The funding and sustainability challenge is, however, becoming ever more acute and it may not be realistic to rule out models that involve some form of user-side payment in all circumstances. This may unreasonably restrict resources from exploring new funding avenues and models. During the development of this White Paper, a number of potential exceptions were highlighted. For example:
 - Some biodata resources have already explored introducing fees for value added services, sometimes focusing primarily on commercial users, whilst retaining free and open access to their core datasets for all users.
 - For managed access resources, where the costs associated with assessing and enabling individual requests to access data will sometimes be non-trivial, it may be reasonable to seek to recover costs through standard charges to users. In addition, further conditions on access may be required to respect data sovereignty and ensure equitable benefit sharing in line with the CARE principles and other international standards.

- The move to cloud-based computing is creating questions of how the associated costs should be provisioned, as the ability of users to access and analyse huge volumes of data grows. Whilst the costs for most research users will be modest, the cost for some high-volume users, for example those working with large-scale genomic or imaging datasets, might be considerable. Funders are increasingly concerned that they cannot commit to providing these costs for all users of a resource.
33. It is suggested that where such approaches are considered, they must always be aligned with maximising the value of the data and promoting global equity. In particular, researchers should not be prevented from accessing and using research data outputs based on their ability to pay. It is also important to note that none of this discussion rules out the participation of commercial funders in participating in cooperative approaches to funding infrastructure.
 34. The sixth principle recognises specifically that many funders will have legal or administrative restrictions on moving funds internationally. Approaches to advance sustainability must, therefore, allow for cases where funders—especially those linked to governments—are required to exert restrictions on the destination of their funds and on where funded activities take place.
 35. The seventh principle emphasises that the development of new cooperative funding models will require biodata resources to adapt their governance structures in order to serve the interests of all stakeholders. In particular, as mechanisms are introduced that allow multiple contributing institutions to support the delivery of a biodata resource, the resource must ensure that it continues to support the needs of its user community. The long term successful operation of a data resource is a shared responsibility: the funders frame the policy, the data resource managers implement the operation and life cycle systems, and the community steers the services while both supplying and exploiting the data.
 36. The eighth principle recognises the fundamental need to maximise the openness of data and metadata as a value multiplier and key to sustainability—maximising usage and enabling data to be linked, allowing users to discover collections of relevant data sets and to integrate cross-domain data sets to support their research questions.

As noted above, it is recognised fully that some data—particularly data relating to research participants—can only be shared through managed access processes, underpinned by appropriate governance processes. In all cases, biodata resources need to seek the right balance, minimising the friction and cost for access to users as far as possible, whilst ensuring proportionate and adequate safeguards are in place in line with the key underlying tenet of “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”.

37. The final principle recognises that support for an essential biodata resource requires a major commitment from its funding organisation(s). While the commitment to support a biodata resource may be made with the greatest intent of long-term support at one time, there is always a risk that changing strategic priorities or funding pressures will mean funding is terminated or reduced. For this reason, it is important that resources work with funders to establish long-term plans for sustainability and succession plans, and work to diversify funding where this helps mitigate any risks associated with reliance on single funders.

2.2 Developing, testing and implementing new cooperative funding mechanisms

38. Given the urgent and growing challenge to the global biodata infrastructure, there is a critical need for funders to put the principles described above into practice and begin to design and test new cooperative funding approaches
39. In the expert discussions and consultation that informed the development of this White Paper, three fundamental points became clear:
- There is no single solution to the sustainability challenge: given the multitude of funders and huge diversity among biodata resources, there will not be a one-size-fits approach. A range of complementary mechanisms will be needed that give different funders the flexibility to contribute in ways that align with their remits and mandates, and enable biodata resources to adopt models that build on their current operations and most effectively and efficiently ensure the continued delivery of services to their user communities.
 - It is vital to build on what is working well: some biodata resources have approaches in place which have worked well to date both from the perspective of the resource and their funders. There is a need to learn from and build on these approaches where they exist and not to replace these mechanisms unnecessarily.
 - There is a need to explore both immediate solutions and long-term approaches: many globally-important biodata resources face imminent and critical challenges for sustainability. Therefore, there is a need to act now and adopt approaches which can be implemented in the short to medium term and which build on existing ways of working. However, it is important in parallel to also consider more innovative and transformative models which might offer more effective and scalable solutions in the longer term.

40. A range of initial models were considered in the development of this White Paper. These models are described and illustrated in more detail in Appendix B. Based on consultation with funders, biodata resources and other stakeholders, two types of approach were identified which stakeholders felt held the most promise, namely:
- Pooled funding models—in which a range of international funders contribute to a common fund, potentially through an agreed formula (which might for example be linked to volume of research spend or levels of usage of included biodata resources among that funder’s research community). This fund would then be allocated between a set group of participating biodata resources through an independent review process the parameters for which have been pre-agreed by the funders involved.
 - Distributed service models—in which funders support institutions in their own countries or regions that deliver specific components or functions of biodata resources (which are managed at global level to provide an integrated service to users), or that provide resources that serve users at national or regional level but which are coordinated at global level so that each national resource provides users with data and tools generated across the global network. Major bioinformatic resource centres at national and regional level (such as EMBL-EBI, NCBI, SIB and DSMZ) play a key role in these models—operating a portfolio of biodata resources, providing shared infrastructure and services across these resources, and coordinating with other centres internationally to deliver federated global resources.
41. Overall, there was a prevailing, but not universal, view that a pooled funding approach would be the optimal solution if it could be implemented effectively in practice and achieve support from funders around the world. However, there was also a strong feeling from many that the political and practical barriers to funders coordinating in this way made it unlikely this could be fully achieved. In general, whilst a worldwide approach in which funders cooperate to support the biodata infrastructure in an equitable and proportionate manner must be our vision, the reality in the near term is that many major funders will not be willing or able to contribute via a pooled fund, and are more likely to contribute to distributed approaches where they retain the agency to support activities at a national or regional level.

42. However, it is important to emphasise that pooled funding mechanisms could still make an important contribution in parallel with other mechanisms, even if not all funders are able to take part. Indeed, they could provide an important way of enabling new types of funders who don't in general provide support for underlying biodata infrastructure to take part—such as commercial entities, international bodies and philanthropies. Pooled funding and distributed models are not mutually exclusive and could run in parallel. Indeed, a biodata resource could very conceivably be supported through both models in combination—with some funders supporting national or regional elements, and other funding for ongoing operations being provided via pooled funding.
43. In summary, each of these mechanisms offer distinct benefits and challenges, which are outlined briefly in Table 1 below, and their suitability and relevance will vary depending on the nature of particular biodata resources and the requirements of individual funders.

Table 1—Key strengths and challenges for pooled funding and distributed service model

Mechanism	Strengths	Challenges
Pooled funding models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allows effective global funding without an additional coordination layer • Allows resources to operate under divergent models most appropriate to their needs • Allows participation of new funders (e.g. International organisations, industry or global philanthropies) who wish to contribute to sustainability at global level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many funders would likely not be prepared to consider this approach in the near term • Problematic for funders whose objects prevent them from funding internationally or who are not able to devolve control of funding decisions • Requires a trusted and commonly agreed broker and process to manage and disburse funds
Distributed service models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allow funders to support activities in their own jurisdictions • For some resources, would build on existing models and partnerships • If operated effectively can add economies of scale and increase global reach 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can add a significant additional coordination/governance layer • Can create challenges around standardisation of data and service delivery • Might not be effective or efficient for smaller targeted resources

44. Other potential mechanisms that were considered during the development of this Paper are outlined briefly below. Although these models were felt to be less widely applicable for most biodata resources, it was recognised that for some biodata resources they may add significant value and be worth exploring further.
45. Distributed personnel models—here, staff supported by funders at institutions within their jurisdictions would contribute to biodata resources globally in line with need, for example through secondments or dedicating part of their time to supporting these resources. The consultation feedback indicated that there would be some significant challenges to this type of approach for many biodata resources and that it was unlikely to be effective on its own in significantly enhancing sustainability, but could be a very useful add on in combination with other approaches.
46. Mixed 'commercial' models—in some circumstances, it may be feasible for resources to generate revenue whilst still providing free and open access to the data they hold. This can include the use of 'freemium' models, where access to the data is free for all, but additional value-added services and tools are offered in return for a fee. There may also be potential for some widely used resources to generate advertising revenue or attract voluntary contributions. Where attempted, such approaches have sometimes failed to generate revenue at a scale required to significantly reduce the long-term dependence of biodata resources on funders (see Gabella et al 2018). Nevertheless, these may be viable and useful additional options for some resources in some circumstances.
47. 'Tax-based' models—models have been proposed in other areas (for example, development of medicines for neglected diseases) where funds for areas of unmet need are generated through a micro-levy on an unrelated transaction (for example, purchase of a ticket for air travel). It seems unlikely that the political will exists at present to implement this type of approach, but this might change in the future.

48. There is a strong need for funders and biodata resources to initiate a range of pilot efforts to test cooperative funding approaches. This should include:
- Working proactively to explore opportunities to expand existing distributed service models and develop new partnerships that bring in new funding partners and enhance sustainability;
 - Designing and testing pooled funding approaches as a way to bring in additional funders to support biodata resources,
 - Supporting biodata resources to develop and test other mechanisms to diversify funding and enhance sustainability—including, but not limited to, the mechanisms described above.
49. There was a strong view from many stakeholders that, in the longer term, existing funding approaches would not scale and that addressing the sustainability challenge would require more radical change to how the world approaches the financing of the world's biodata infrastructure. It was emphasised that there may be important lessons and thinking that can be drawn from disciplines beyond the life sciences, such as economics, and from the commercial sector.
50. Funders, biodata resources and the wider life sciences research community should in parallel explore models and ideas used in other disciplines and sectors, engaging with experts from these diverse fields to identify models with the power to transform the problem even if these challenge existing norms and ways of working.

2.3 Coordinating support for research funders in sustaining the global biodata infrastructure

51. Alongside work to develop new funding approaches, there is a critical need for funders to work together at a global level to ensure that the global biodata infrastructure as a whole is developed and sustained over time—maximising the connections between resources, embedding standards and good practices, and responding to technological developments and evolving needs of user communities. As an organisation specifically convened by funders to address the sustainability challenge, GBC should take a leading role in this work.
52. First and foremost, the long term sustainability of the global infrastructure will require a greater and more diverse range of funders to provide support for biodata resources and to participate in cooperative funding approaches. This will require enhanced advocacy efforts to engage funders and raise awareness of the critical importance of the sustainability challenge, underpinned by work to build the evidence base for the value, impact and return on investment of biodata resources.
53. In addition to increasing and stabilising funding for biodata resources, the long-term sustainability of the global biodata infrastructure has several key elements, which include:
 - Coverage—filling gaps in current provision across scientific domains, data types, and emerging needs;
 - Responsiveness—ensuring that the infrastructure evolves to meet emerging technological needs and anticipates the needs of research and user communities;
 - Service standards—services are stable, and embed appropriate technical and good practice standards to serve the needs of funders and researchers.
 - Connectivity—appropriate interconnectivities are developed and maintained both between resources within the infrastructure and between biodata resources in neighbouring fields and domains.

- Capacity—the infrastructure has the technical and resource capacity to manage data volumes and usage requirements
- Inclusiveness—the infrastructure is globally inclusive and any barriers to participation are minimised
- Efficiency—the infrastructure operates in a manner that seeks to maximise efficiencies, economies of scale and cost effectiveness

54. Funders and biodata resources must cooperate to anticipate and address these aspects of sustainability, to identify and discuss emerging trends and needs and to develop good practice principles for managing biodata resources across the lifecycle (establishing, sustaining and sunsetting).

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Appendices

Appendix A—Development of the White Paper

In early 2022, the GBC’s Board of Funders established two cross-funder Working Groups: one to explore the topic of Sustainability and a second to examine Open Data Strategies. Both Working Groups brought together senior representatives from GBC member and observer organisations and were chaired by the Board Chair. Each group was tasked with developing a Consultation Paper to explore the challenges and to set out ways forward for consideration by the GBC Board and consultation with the GBC’s wider stakeholder community.

The GBC Board Working Group on Sustainability was tasked with identifying ways that funders could cooperate to fund data resources in a more sustainable manner, and had two key objectives:

- To identify and share best practice for individual funders—the Working Group explored challenges faced by individual funders that support biodata resources, and opportunities for funders to develop more strategic and sustainable approaches for supporting the biodata resources that they fund.
- To explore ways funders could cooperate internationally to sustain the global biodata resource infrastructure—the Group developed a series of premises, principles and models for cross-funder partnerships to more equitably and reliably fund biodata resources critical to the global life science and biomedical research communities and explored ways in which funders could cooperate to develop and sustain the biodata infrastructure as a whole.

The Consultation Paper that resulted from the Group’s discussions set out the issues and challenges around biodata sustainability and set out an initial series of options and ideas. These options were discussed by the GBC’s Board of Funders and refined further by the Working Group based on the Board’s feedback.

The GBC Secretariat then ran a targeted consultation process to gather feedback from key GBC stakeholders on the Consultation Paper. This comprised two main elements:

- Group Discussions with key GBC Governance and Advisory Groups—the Consultation Paper was discussed by the GBC’s Scientific Advisory Committee (SAC) at an in-person meeting in July 2023, and by the GCBR Forum at a virtual meeting in September 2023. Members of the SAC and GCBR Forum were also invited to respond individually to the community consultation (see below).
- Community Consultation—the Consultation Paper was published on the GBC Zenodo channel and featured on the GBC website, and linked to a structured Google Form for feedback. The Consultation was communicated via targeted emails to key GBC stakeholder groups and organisations active in biodata resource funding and open science spheres. The Consultation period ran from 2 October 2023 to 22 January 2024.

Through the community consultation, 21 responses were received from GBC stakeholders including resource managers, researchers, and representatives of infrastructure providers and standards organisations. Taken together with the detailed comments and advice provided by the SAC and GCBR Forum, the consultation provided a large amount of valuable feedback on the options set out in the consultation paper and helped shape the position set out in this white paper.

Appendix B—Cooperative funding mechanisms for sustaining biodata resources

A brief summary of the cooperative funding mechanisms discussed in the White Paper follows below.

Pooled Funding

In this type of mechanism, a group of funders would contribute to a common fund, which is then allocated between an agreed set of biodata resources via a centralised mechanism. The specifics of how such a fund would operate would need to be set by the participating funders. It is anticipated that if this model was applied globally, the contributions of individual funders might be set in proportion to their total research spend in relevant fields (i.e. life sciences and biomedical research) or in proportion to the actual or estimated usage of the resources included. Although establishing a reliable process to assess the latter would currently be problematic.

It is anticipated that a trusted third party would administer the fund—running an independent expert review process to determine how the fund is disbursed among participating resources, with parameters agreed by participants. In an ideal scenario, participating funders would not place conditions on the resources or geographies into which the funds they contribute could be disbursed, but there is the possibility of accommodating such requirements should the pool of participating funders grow sufficiently large.

Distributed service or consortia-based funding

This model would allow funders to support specific institutions within their local countries or regions to run standalone resources or specific components of resources, which are then coordinated at global level. This broad type of mechanism encompasses a spectrum of possible approaches.

Under one type of approach, funders would support institutions to deliver specific components, activities or functions of a biodata resource. The biodata resource would then coordinate these disbursed components to deliver a single resource (for example, with a single user interface and unified user services). Under this model, such resources would be highly distributed with sub-components at a variety of institutions around the world.

A related approach would be for funders to support resources at national or regional level that provide an interface and services that are tailored for users based in the region (to deposit and access data). These resources then coordinate at global level, to—for example—apply common data standards and mirror data, such that each national or regional resource provides access to the entire global dataset, and—where appropriate—a common set of analytical tools. The regionally coordinated approach is illustrated below.

This type of mechanism could also incorporate consortia-based approaches where a set of data resources working with related data types coordinate activities to provide interoperable services and potentially share component functions where this might add efficiencies and aid sustainability.

Other Models considered: Distributed personnel

This is an alternative, but potentially complementary approach where funders pay for activities in institutions and staff at those institutions then contribute to resources globally in line with need, through for example secondments or dedicating part of their time to supporting resources based elsewhere.

The consultation feedback suggested that this type of model might be difficult to implement in practice, as data curators often require specific dedicated training to work for specific data resources. It was also not felt to be sufficient on its own to ensure sustainability. It was felt however that it could be a useful add on to other models—particularly the distributed service model. If implemented effectively, this type of approach could aid in fostering clearer career paths, job security and professional development for data managers and curators.

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